

EFFECTIVENESS OF FLIPPED CLASSROOM AND DIRECT INSTRUCTION IN IMPROVING THE WRITING SKILLS OF GRADE 10 LEARNERS

Deah T. Pagara, Revina O. Mendoza, PhD

English Department, Lourdes College Graduate School, Cagayan De Oro City, Misamis Oriental, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19599181>

ABSTRACT

Junior high school students today face persistent challenges in academic writing, particularly in developing clear arguments, organizing ideas, and maintaining grammatical accuracy. However, limited studies in the Philippine junior high school context have examined how specific instructional strategies influence distinct dimensions of writing performance. Grounded in Constructivist Learning Theory, which emphasizes active engagement and scaffolding, this study evaluated the effectiveness of Flipped Classroom and Direct Instruction among Grade 10 learners. Employing a quasi-experimental design, two groups underwent their respective instructional interventions over six weeks. Pretest and posttest assessments measured progress across four components: topic development, clarity of position, organization, and language use. Both groups showed measurable improvement in their mean scores after the intervention. However, only the learners in the Flipped Classroom advanced to the Good level of performance, while the Direct Instruction group remained within the Fair range. Multivariate analysis further indicated that learners exposed to the flipped classroom achieved significantly higher posttest scores in topic development, clarity of position, and organization, while improvements in language use were comparable between groups. These findings suggest that the flipped classroom approach exerts a stronger influence on higher-order writing skills, enabling learners to better develop ideas, articulate positions, and structure their work. Direct Instruction, however, remains effective in reinforcing foundational language accuracy. Future research may examine the long-term effects of flipped classroom strategies across grade levels and writing genres.

Keywords: *Flipped Classroom, Writing Skills, Quasi-experimental, Argumentative Essay*

INTRODUCTION

Writing is one of the four macro skills essential in learning English as a foreign language, alongside listening, speaking, and reading. Among these, writing is often considered the most complex productive skill because it requires the integration of vocabulary, grammar, organization, and critical thinking (Singca, 2024; Alotaibi, 2020). Proficiency in writing is vital not only for academic achievement but also for lifelong communication and professional success, making it a cornerstone of holistic literacy development.

Despite its importance, many Filipino learners continue to struggle with writing. Local studies reveal persistent difficulties across grade levels. Saavedra and Barredo (2020) found that elementary pupils in the Zamboanga Peninsula faced challenges in vocabulary, spelling, grammar, and sentence construction. Morales (2021) reported similar problems among Grade 7 students in Davao Oriental, while Barayuga et al. (2024) noted that senior high school students in Davao de Oro to express ideas coherently. Ondes (2024) further observed that Grade 10 learners in modular distance learning exhibited inconsistent writing literacy, marked by grammatical, organizational, and mechanical weaknesses. These findings underscore the inadequacy of traditional, teacher-centered approaches that often limit peer interaction and engagement in the writing process.

International research offers promising alternatives to address these challenges. Zhao and Yang (2023) demonstrated that a social media-supported flipped classroom improved EFL learners' writing performance and reduced anxiety in China. Putri et al (2024) found that Indonesian tertiary students achieved significant gains in essay writing and valued flipped learning for maximizing class time. Similarly, Challob (2021) reported that flipped learning enhanced writing performance, autonomy, and motivation among Iraqi learners. Collectively, these studies affirm that flipped classrooms can strengthen writing proficiency, confidence, and learner engagement across diverse contexts.

However, few local investigations have examined the effectiveness of flipped learning in improving the writing skills of Grade 10 learners in Philippine public schools. The problem addressed in this study, therefore, is the persistent difficulty in writing proficiency among Filipino students and the absence of empirical evidence on whether flipped classroom pedagogy can serve as an effective alternative to direct instruction in improving the writing skills of grade 10 learners.

The researcher was prompted to conduct this study because she observed that her students have difficulty organizing ideas and often struggle to structure essays. They were also observed to commit frequent errors in subject-verb agreement and often have trouble supporting opinions or developing arguments logically.

Moreover, by exploring this gap, the study aimed to inform educators and policymakers on strategies that foster student-centered learning and contribute to the

United Nations' Sustainable Development Goal 4 on Quality Education. Hence, the use of Flipped Classroom and Direct Instruction to improve Grade 10 students' writing skills aligns with SDG 4: Quality Education, as it promotes inclusive, effective, and engaging learning that strengthens literacy and prepares students for lifelong learning.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

This study is anchored in the assumption that both Flipped Learning and Direct Instruction can improve students' writing skills, drawing from four complementary learning theories: the Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning (CTML) proposed by Mayer (2009), Constructivist Learning Theory (Vygotsky, 1978), Self-Determination Theory (SDT) by Deci and Ryan (1985), and Skinner's Behaviorist Theory (1953). CTML posits that learners process information more effectively when it is presented through both visual and auditory channels, making multimedia tools such as video lectures and interactive materials particularly beneficial. In the context of flipped classrooms, this theory is applied through pre-class exposure to digital content, which helps reduce cognitive load and allows learners to allocate more cognitive resources to higher-order writing tasks during class time (Kim & Kim, 2021; Sun & Gao, 2022). Constructivist Learning Theory further supports this approach by emphasizing that learning is an active, reflective, and social process in which learners construct knowledge through interaction and experience. Flipped classrooms embody this principle by promoting peer collaboration, discussions, and guided writing activities, while Direct Instruction aligns with constructivism through structured scaffolding, where teachers model writing strategies and provide corrective feedback within learners' zones of proximal development. Meanwhile, Self-Determination Theory explains the motivational dimension of learning, asserting that students are more engaged when their needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness are fulfilled. Lastly, Skinner's Behaviorist Theory (1953), which emphasizes structured, sequenced lessons and observable changes in learner behavior through positive reinforcement (Addaeroby & Febriani, 2024). Flipped learning fosters autonomy through self-paced pre-class preparation and enhances relatedness through collaborative in-class activities, whereas Direct Instruction supports competence and relatedness through clear guidance and consistent feedback. Together, these theories provide a comprehensive framework for understanding how both instructional approaches facilitate cognitive processing, knowledge construction, and motivation in the development of writing skills.

The study focused on four target writing skills:

1. Topic Development – presenting organized reasons, evidence, and conclusions.
2. Clarity of Position – expressing a main argument clearly.
3. Organization – sequencing ideas coherently.
4. Language Use – applying vocabulary, grammar, and style effectively.

Both approaches aimed to improve these skills but differed in instructional delivery: Direct Instruction emphasized teacher-led modeling and guided exercises, while the Flipped Classroom emphasized pre-class preparation and collaborative in-class application.

Research Questions

This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the writing performance levels of Grade 10 learners before and after the intervention?
2. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest writing performance of the two groups of Grade 10 learners?
3. Which intervention is more effective in improving the writing performance of the Grade 10 learners?

METHODOLOGY

The study involved two intact Grade 10 classes, 35 students each, from a public high school during the 2025–2026 academic year. Purposive sampling ensured classroom integrity. Eligibility criteria included enrollment in Grade 10, regular attendance, and consent/assent from students and parents. A quasi-experimental, non-equivalent groups pretest–posttest design was used. One group received flipped instruction, and the other received conventional Direct Instruction. Students wrote a 300–500 word argumentative essay, “Online Games: Productive or Not Productive,” evaluated on four criteria: Topic Development, Clarity of Position, Organization, and Language Use. The same rubric was used for pretests and posttests to ensure consistency.

The procedures implemented in this study varied according to the instructional approach assigned to each group. In the Flipped Classroom condition, students were provided with pre-class materials, including video lectures and selected readings, which introduced key concepts related to writing such as effective language use, essay structure, topic development and clarity of position. This prior exposure enabled learners to come to class prepared, allowing classroom time to be devoted to higher-order learning activities. During in-class sessions, students engaged in drafting essays, participating in peer review, and taking part in guided writing workshops facilitated by the teacher, who provided immediate feedback and support. In contrast, the Direct Instruction approach followed a more traditional, teacher-centered format. Classroom sessions primarily consisted of teacher-led lectures, explicit explanations of writing concepts, and the presentation of model examples, followed by short guided exercises to reinforce learning. Extended writing tasks, such as essay drafting and revision, were typically assigned as homework, with teacher feedback focusing mainly on correctness and structure.

The data collected in this study were analyzed using appropriate statistical techniques to address the research objectives. Descriptive statistics, including mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage, were employed to summarize and describe the participants’ writing performance before and after the interventions. To determine whether there were significant improvements within each group, paired sample t-tests were conducted to compare pretest and posttest scores. Furthermore, a Multivariate Analysis of Covariance (MANCOVA) was utilized to compare posttest scores between the Flipped Classroom and Direct Instruction groups while controlling for

baseline performance. Prior to conducting MANCOVA, its underlying assumptions—namely normality, homogeneity of variance–covariance matrices, linearity, absence of multicollinearity, and independence of observations—were verified to ensure the validity and reliability of the results (Field, 2018; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019).

RESULTS

Table 1 Summary of Participants’ Writing Skills Before and After the Intervention

Writing Skills	Flipped Classroom				Direct Instruction			
	Pretest		Posttest		Pretest		Posttest	
	Mean	Int	Mean	Int	Mean	Int	Mean	Int
Topic Development	1.67	F	3.04	G	1.93	F	2.64	G
Clarity of Writer’s Position	1.66	F	2.94	G	1.87	F	2.37	F
Organization	1.56	F	2.93	G	1.56	F	2.39	F
Language Use	1.61	F	2.76	G	1.70	F	2.51	G
Overall Mean	1.63	F	2.92	G	1.77	F	2.48	F

Legend: 4.51 – 5.00 O = Outstanding, 3.51 – 4.50 VG = Very Good, 2.51 – 3.50 G = Good, 1.51 – 2.50 F = Fair, 1.00 – 1.50 P = Poor

The results reveal that both the Flipped Classroom and Direct Instruction groups improved, but the magnitude of gains differed. In topic development, the Flipped Classroom group achieved a larger increase (from 1.67 to 3.04) compared to Direct Instruction (from 1.93 to 2.64), indicating stronger progress in constructing well-supported arguments. Similarly, in clarity of position, the Flipped group advanced from 1.66 to 2.94, while the Direct Instruction group rose from 1.87 to 2.37, showing that the flipped approach enabled learners to sustain clearer and more consistent stances. In terms of organization, the Flipped group improved from 1.56 to 2.93, whereas the Direct Instruction group increased from 1.56 to 2.39, suggesting that the flipped method fostered more coherent sequencing of ideas. Finally, in language use, the Flipped group progressed from 1.61 to 2.76, while the Direct Instruction group moved from 1.70 to 2.51, reflecting broader gains in grammatical accuracy and stylistic refinement under the flipped approach. Overall, the findings demonstrate that although both instructional methods improved learners’ writing proficiency, the Flipped Classroom consistently produced greater improvements across all dimensions, moving more learners beyond the Fair level into higher categories of performance.

Table 2 Multivariate Analysis of Covariance (MANCOVA) Summary Table for Posttest Scores with Pretest Scores as Covariates

Writing Skills	Flipped Classroom			Conventional Approach			F(1,64)	p
	M	Int	SD	M	Int	SD		
Topic Development	3.04	G	1.02	2.64	G	0.74	4.451*	0.039

Clarity of Writers' Position	2.94	G	1.05	2.37	G	0.79	8.331*	0.005
Organization	2.93	G	1.20	2.39	G	0.99	5.861*	0.018
Language Use	2.76	G	1.04	2.51	G	1.12	1.117	0.295

Multivariate Analysis

Wilks' $\Lambda = 0.835$ $F(4,61) = 3.004^*$ $p = 0.025$ Partial $\eta^2 = 0.165$

*Note. M = mean, Int = Interpretation SD = standard deviation, Partial η^2 = effect size. Effect size interpretation: 0.01 to 0.05 is small, 0.06 to 0.13 is medium, above or equal 0.14 is large, Legend: 4.51 – 5.00 O = Outstanding, 3.51 – 4.50 VG = Very Good, 2.51 – 3.50 G = Good, 1.51 – 2.50 F = Fair, 1.00 – 1.50 P = Poor. *Significant at 0.05 two-tailed alpha level.*

The within-group analyses revealed that both instructional approaches significantly improved the writing skills of Grade 10 learners. For the Flipped Classroom group, the Repeated Measures Multivariate Analysis of Variance (RM-MANOVA) indicated a substantial overall improvement in writing performance, Wilks' $\Lambda = 0.207$, $F(4,31) = 29.736$, $p < .001$, with a large effect size (partial $\eta^2 = 0.793$). Paired t-tests further confirmed significant gains across all subcomponents, including Topic Development, Clarity of Position, Organization, and Language Use, with t-values ranging from 8.355 to 9.936 ($p < .001$). Similarly, the Direct Instruction group demonstrated significant overall improvement, Wilks' $\Lambda = 0.161$, $F(4,31) = 40.359$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.839$, with all writing subcomponents showing significant gains ($t = 7.737$ – 12.272 , $p < .001$). Between-group comparisons using MANCOVA revealed a statistically significant difference in posttest writing performance between the two approaches, Wilks' $\Lambda = 0.835$, $F(4,61) = 3.004$, $p = 0.025$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.165$. Specifically, the Flipped Classroom group outperformed the Direct Instruction group in Topic Development ($F = 4.451$, $p = 0.039$), Clarity of Position ($F = 8.331$, $p = 0.005$), and Organization ($F = 5.861$, $p = 0.018$), while no significant difference was observed in Language Use ($F = 1.117$, $p = 0.295$). These findings suggest that although both approaches effectively improve writing skills, the Flipped Classroom offers greater advantages in developing higher-order components of writing, such as idea generation, clarity, and structural organization.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study demonstrate that both the Flipped Classroom and Direct Instruction approaches significantly improved the writing performance of Grade 10 learners across the four dimensions of Topic Development, Clarity of Writer's Position, Organization, and Language Use. The consistently higher gains in Topic Development, Clarity of Position, and Organization observed in the Flipped Classroom can be attributed to its learner-centered design, which combines pre-class preparation with active, collaborative in-class engagement. As Lo and Hew (2020) and Santos and Serpa (2020) emphasized, flipped learning restructures instruction by shifting lectures to pre-class materials, thereby freeing classroom time for higher-order tasks such as drafting, peer review, and guided workshops. This design reduces cognitive load, builds confidence, and addresses common barriers in writing development such as limited vocabulary, grammatical difficulties, and writing anxiety (Ignacio, 2025; Putri, 2022). By providing learners with foundational knowledge beforehand and engaging them in interactive, feedback-rich activities during class, the flipped approach promotes the construction,

organization, and defense of ideas more effectively, consistent with the principles of Constructivist Learning Theory (Vygotsky, 1978).

Direct Instruction also resulted in statistically significant improvements across all writing components, demonstrating that structured, teacher-led methods remain effective in developing writing proficiency. Its strength lies in explicit modeling, guided practice, and consistent reinforcement, which are particularly effective for foundational aspects of writing, including grammar, vocabulary, and overall correctness. This explains why gains in Language Use were comparable between the two approaches, as explicit, teacher-centered instruction is well-suited for developing technical accuracy in writing (Cabigao, 2021; Apolonio, 2023). While Direct Instruction strengthened basic conventions, its influence on higher-order skills such as idea development and organization was relatively limited, likely due to reduced opportunities for extended, interactive writing practice during class.

The comparative analysis further confirmed that the Flipped Classroom outperformed Direct Instruction in Topic Development, Clarity of Position, and Organization, highlighting that higher-order writing skills are best supported in learner-centered, interactive environments that encourage autonomy, collaboration, and timely feedback (Mohammad & Khan, 2022; Goshu & Gebremariam, 2024). In contrast, Language Use showed no significant difference between the approaches, reinforcing the view that accuracy-oriented skills benefit from explicit instruction regardless of the instructional model. These results underscore that writing proficiency is multifaceted: mastery of foundational mechanics and grammar (language use) is essential, but higher-order skills require opportunities for cognitive engagement, social interaction, and reflective practice.

Overall, the findings suggest that effective writing instruction should integrate both approaches. Direct Instruction provides a strong foundation in accuracy and correctness, while the Flipped Classroom extends learning to higher-order cognitive processes, fostering autonomy, engagement, and critical thinking. A blended strategy that combines the strengths of both methods may provide the most holistic support for developing proficient, confident, and independent writers.

Conclusions

Learners in both the flipped classroom and Direct Instruction groups demonstrated improvement in their writing skills over time, with greater gains observed in higher-order skills such as topic development, clarity of position, and organization compared to language use. This suggests that structured writing experiences—whether innovative or traditional—can support the progressive development of writing proficiency.

Both the flipped classroom and Direct Instruction groups showed statistically significant improvements in their writing skills from pretest to posttest, indicating that both approaches are effective in improving topic development, writer's clarity of position, organization, and language use.

There is a statistically significant difference in posttest writing performance between the two groups, with the flipped classroom group achieving higher scores. This indicates that flipped learning is more effective in improving higher-order writing skills, while Direct Instruction remain useful for strengthening foundational aspects of writing.

This study offers meaningful insights into how different instructional approaches—Flipped Classroom and Direct Instruction—contribute to the development of students' writing skills in distinct yet complementary ways. Both approaches were found to significantly improve learners' writing performance, confirming that structured instruction, whether innovative or traditional, plays a crucial role in improving writing proficiency. However, the Flipped Classroom demonstrated stronger effects on higher-order skills such as Topic Development, Clarity of Position, and Organization, while Direct Instruction was particularly effective in reinforcing foundational aspects such as Language Use.

These findings support the principles of Constructivist Learning Theory, which emphasize active engagement, collaboration, and knowledge construction. The flipped approach created opportunities for learners to interact, reflect, and refine their ideas through guided practice and peer collaboration, leading to improvements in idea development and organization. At the same time, the effectiveness of Direct Instruction reflects Behaviorist principles, where structured practice, repetition, and immediate feedback contribute to accuracy and skill mastery.

Rather than positioning one approach as superior, the results indicate that both serve important roles in writing instruction. The Flipped Classroom fosters autonomy, critical thinking, and engagement, while Direct Instruction provides the structure and clarity necessary for mastering foundational skills. Therefore, a blended instructional model that integrates the strengths of both approaches may offer the most effective pathway for developing well-rounded writing proficiency among learners. Such an approach ensures that students not only learn how to write correctly but also how to think critically, organize ideas, and express themselves effectively.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that teachers adopt a more balanced instructional approach by integrating flipped classroom strategies with conventional teaching methods. Providing pre-class materials such as video lectures, readings, and model texts can help students build foundational knowledge before class, while in-class time can be maximized for active learning activities such as drafting, peer review, and collaborative discussions. This combination allows learners to develop both higher-order writing skills and foundational competencies simultaneously.

School administrators play a crucial role in supporting the successful implementation of such approaches. It is recommended that they provide professional development programs focused on flipped learning pedagogy to equip teachers with the necessary skills and strategies. Additionally, investment in ICT infrastructure and ensuring equitable access to digital resources are essential to make flipped learning

feasible and effective across diverse educational contexts. Encouraging the adoption of blended learning models can further enhance teaching practices and student outcomes.

For curriculum developers, the findings highlight the importance of designing instructional materials and modules that emphasize key writing components, including Topic Development, Clarity of Position, Organization, and Language Use. Flexible lesson plans that incorporate both structured guidance and student-centered activities can help teachers adapt instruction to different learning environments and student needs.

Finally, future researchers are encouraged to build on this study by exploring the long-term effects of flipped learning on writing proficiency through longitudinal research designs. Investigating hybrid models that combine digital tools with flipped pedagogy may also provide deeper insights into improving writing instruction. Additionally, further studies should examine challenges related to technology access, teacher readiness, and student motivation, particularly within the Philippine educational context, to ensure that innovative approaches are both effective and sustainable.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Data collection adhered to a methodical procedure for precision and ethical validation. Before the pretest was conducted, the researcher sought ethical clearance from the Research Ethics (REC) of Lourdes College. Formal approval was then obtained from the Schools Division Office and the school head. Parental permission and learner assent were secured, and participants received an explanation of the study's objectives, including the option to decline or withdraw at any time. Both groups took a pretest before the experimental group was introduced to the flipped classroom intervention, while the control group received traditional instruction. A posttest was administered to both groups six weeks later.

The research was guided by the Belmont Principles (National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects, 2020). Respect for persons was ensured by obtaining informed consent and protecting the interests of participants. Beneficence was preserved by reducing risks and aligning the intervention with curriculum objectives. Fairness was achieved by treating participants equitably and ensuring that all learners gained access to the instructional resources following the completion of the study. Privacy was protected through the use of codes to identify participants and by reporting findings in aggregate form. All information was stored securely and applied solely for academic purposes.

REFERENCES

- Addaeroby, M., & Febriani, E. (2024). Application of Skinner's Behaviorist Learning Theory in learning Arabic Speaking Proficiency/ Penerapan Teori Belajar Behavioristik Skinner Dalam Pembelajaran Maharah Kalam. *Jurnal Bahasa Arab*. <https://doi.org/10.69988/mx5kzs45>.
- Apolonio, J. (2023). Effectiveness of "How to Write a Sentence" as Instructional Material to Improve the Writing Skills of Grade 6 Pupils. *International Journal of*

Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education
Research <https://doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.04.03.25>.

- Alotaibi, H. (2020). Exploring writing difficulties among EFL learners. *English Language Teaching*, 13(2), 98–107. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v13n2p98>
- Barayuga, J., Dela Peña, R., & Villanueva, M. (2024). Senior high school students' writing difficulties: Basis for intervention program. *Lorenzo S. Sarmiento Sr. National High School Research Journal*, 6(2), 45–59
- Cabigao, J. (2021). Improving the Basic Writing Skills of Grade 7 Learners in Filipino: An Action Research in Filipino Language. *Education 3-13*, 9, 67-71. <https://doi.org/10.34293/education.v9i3.3815>.
- Challob, A. (2021). The effect of flipped classroom on EFL learners' writing performance, autonomy, and motivation. *International Journal of English Language Education*, 9(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijele.v9i1.18345>
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). *Intrinsic motivation and self-determination in human behavior*. Springer.
- Johnson, R. B., & Christensen, L. (2020). *Educational research: Quantitative, qualitative, and mixed approaches* (7th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Goshu, T., & Gebremariam, H. (2024). Teacher-student writing conferences and their effects on organization, vocabulary, and mechanics. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 12(3), 145–162.
- Ignacio, J. (2025). Pre-writing strategies and writing proficiency: Correlations and barriers. *Philippine Journal of Educational Research*, 17(2), 55–70.
- Kim, S., & Kim, H. (2021). *Multimedia learning in EFL writing: Applications of Mayer's CTML*.
- Mohammad, A., & Khan, S. (2022). Flipped classroom and EFL writing: Effects on grammatical accuracy and motivation. *TESOL Quarterly*, 56(3), 789–812.
- Morales, J. (2021). Writing challenges of Grade 7 students in Davao Oriental: Implications for teaching strategies. *Philippine Journal of Basic Education*, 5(1), 112–125.
- Mayer, R. E. (2009). *Multimedia learning* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research. (2020). *The Belmont report: Ethical principles and guidelines for the protection of human subjects of research*. U.S. Department of Health & Human Services. <https://www.hhs.gov/ohrp/regulations-and-policy/belmont-report>
- Ondes, R. (2024). Writing literacy of Grade 10 learners in modular distance learning. *Mindanao Journal of Educational Research*, 12(3), 77–89.
- Putri, A., Cahyono, B., & Zubaidi, A. (2024). Flipped learning in essay writing: Indonesian tertiary students' perceptions and performance. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 15(2), 210–220. <https://doi.org/10.17507/jltr.1502.05>
- Lo, C. K., & Hew, K. F. (2020). A critical review of flipped classroom challenges in K–12 education. *Educational Research Review*, 31, 100326. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2020.100326>

- Santos, A., & Serpa, S. (2020). The flipped classroom as a restructuring of the teaching-learning process. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 9(3), 112–118.
- Saavedra, A. D., & Barredo, C. P. (2020). Factors that contribute to the poor writing skills in Filipino and English of the elementary pupils. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 14(5), 1090–1105.
- Singca, R. (2024). Integrating critical thinking in EFL writing instruction. *Asian EFL Journal*, 26(4), 56–72.
- Skinner, B. F. (1953). *Science and human behavior*. New York: Macmillan.
- Sun, Y., & Gao, F. (2022). Flipped learning and multimedia input in EFL writing: Reducing cognitive overload. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 35(8), 1123–1140. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2020.1868532>
- Tabachnick, B. G., & Fidell, L. S. (2019). *Using multivariate statistics* (7th ed.). Pearson.
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Harvard University Press.
- Zhao, Y., & Yang, L. (2023). Social media-supported flipped classroom in EFL writing: Effects on performance and anxiety. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 36(7), 650–670. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2021.1958112>